

A Prospective Observational Study on Prevalence, Risk Factors, and Management of Lower Respiratory Tract Infections at a Tertiary Care Teaching Hospital

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Abstract: This study examined the occurrence, influencing factors, and treatment approaches for Lower Respiratory Tract Infections (LRTIs) in the General Medicine Department of Basaweshwar Teaching and General Hospital, Kalaburagi, over six months. Participants aged 18 and above, of both genders, diagnosed with LRTIs, were included in this prospective observational study. Data from 100 cases were collected using structured forms to analyze the prevalence, risk factors, and management strategies for LRTIs. The findings revealed that males constituted the majority (60%) of LRTI cases, with a higher prevalence observed in individuals under 60 years of age. Pneumonia emerged as the most prevalent LRTI subtype (40%). Diagnosis relied on clinical, radiological, and laboratory assessments, with imaging modalities such as X-ray and CT scans frequently employed. Streptococcus pneumoniae was commonly identified as the causative microorganism through sputum smear examinations. Clinical symptoms primarily included cough, shortness of breath, fever, and pulmonary congestion. Commonly prescribed antibiotics included Amoxicillin + Clavulanate, Ceftriaxone, Levofloxacin, and nebulized inhalational drugs such as Salbutamol and Albuterol. Weakened immune systems (76%) were identified as the primary risk factor, followed by age, gender, and habits like smoking and alcohol consumption. Nineteen cases experienced recurrence during the study period. In conclusion, this study documented 100 cases of LRTIs over six months, with a male predominance and pneumonia as the most frequent subtype, particularly affecting individuals below 60 years old. Weakened immune systems, age, male gender, and habits like smoking and alcohol consumption were significant risk factors. However, the lack of consistent sputum examination highlighted a gap in clinical practice essential for specific treatment.

Keywords: Lower Respiratory Tract Infections; Pneumonia; Streptococcus; Risk Factors; Immunity.

1. Introduction

Respiratory tract infections (RTIs) are contagious diseases that affect the respiratory system, with upper respiratory tract infections (URTIs) and lower respiratory tract infections (LRTIs) being the two main categories. While URTIs, such as the common cold, are typically mild, LRTIs like pneumonia are more serious and can impose significant burdens on society. These infections are frequent reasons for medical visits and hospitalizations, ranging from minor illnesses to potentially life-threatening conditions. The severity of an infection depends on both the virulence of the infecting organism and the strength of the host's immune response. Moreover, the bacterial strains causing LRTIs can vary between countries and change over time within the same country. [1]

Upper Respiratory Tract Infections (URTIs) affect the portion of the air passages situated above the vocal cords, encompassing structures such as the nose, sinuses, throat, and larynx. Common infections within this area comprise tonsillitis, pharyngitis, laryngitis, sinusitis, middle ear infections, specific strains of influenza, and the common cold. Symptoms associated with URTIs may include coughing, a sore throat, nasal discharge, nasal congestion, headaches, mild fever, facial discomfort, and sneezing. [2]

Lower Respiratory Tract Infections (LRTIs) affect the parts of the respiratory system below the vocal cords, including the trachea, bronchial tubes, bronchioles, and lungs. Generally, LRTIs tend to be more serious compared to upper respiratory infections. They represent a significant cause of mortality among infectious diseases. Bronchitis and pneumonia are the two predominant types of LRTIs. [3]

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Lower respiratory tract infections rank as the fifth leading cause of death globally and represent the primary infectious cause of death, contributing to approximately 2.74 million deaths worldwide. This estimate closely aligns with findings from the 2010 Global Burden of Disease study. However, this figure only considers infections caused by *Streptococcus pneumoniae* and *Haemophilus influenzae*, thus underestimating the overall disease burden as it doesn't include atypical or nosocomial causes. The prevalence rates for hospital-acquired (HA) and community-acquired (CA) lower respiratory tract infections (LRTIs) were found to be 2.4% and 6.1%, respectively, indicating an increase compared to earlier reports. Additionally, the prevalence rate of HA infections among ventilated patients stood at 18.6%. [4]

Common lower respiratory tract infections encompass various conditions:

- Chronic Obstructive Pulmonary Disorder (COPD): This condition comprises a range of diseases leading to airflow obstruction and respiratory difficulties.
- Influenza (Flu): This viral infection can impact either the upper or lower respiratory system.
- Bronchitis: Characterized by the infection of air passages.
- Pneumonia: An infection affecting the lungs.
- Bronchiolitis: This condition triggers inflammation and congestion within the small airways (bronchioles) of the lungs. [5]

Chronic obstructive pulmonary disease (COPD) is a persistent inflammatory lung condition that obstructs airflow from the lungs. Symptoms typically include difficulty breathing, coughing, production of mucus (sputum), and wheezing. The primary cause is often prolonged exposure to irritants like cigarette smoke or environmental pollutants. Individuals with COPD face an elevated risk of developing heart disease, lung cancer, and various other health issues. Chronic bronchitis, on the other hand, is inflammation of the bronchial tube lining, responsible for transporting air to and from the lung air sacs (alveoli). It manifests as a persistent daily cough and mucus production. [6]

The following recommendations are suggested for the empirical antibiotic treatment of COPD exacerbations, with the option to adjust treatment if a specific pathogen is identified. First-line antibiotics include Doxycycline and Amoxicillin, while second-line options consist of Co-amoxiclav, Clarithromycin, and Cefixime. Although various other drugs are proposed for COPD exacerbation treatment, Azithromycin is not recommended due to its inferior activity against *Streptococcus pneumoniae* compared to Clarithromycin. Ciprofloxacin's efficacy against *S. pneumoniae* alone is deemed insufficient, although it shows utility against *Influenza* and *Moraxella catarrhalis*. Levofloxacin, the active isomer of Ofloxacin, doesn't offer significant microbiological benefits. Moxifloxacin, a quinolone, is effective against Gram-negative organisms like *Haemophilus* and *Moraxella*, and it exhibits greater activity against Gram-positives such as *S. pneumoniae*. Despite its efficacy, its usage is constrained by the increased risk of *Clostridium difficile* infection (CDI) associated with quinolones and the rare occurrence of severe hepatotoxicity. [7]

The management of lower respiratory tract infections (LRTIs) typically begins with general practitioners (GPs). However, the use of antibiotic prescriptions in LRTIs remains a subject of debate. On one hand, LRTIs often have a bacterial origin, leading to significant morbidity and mortality, necessitating prompt antibiotic treatment. On the other hand, distinguishing between LRTIs and community-acquired pneumonia (CAP) in outpatients can be challenging, with many cases being self-limiting illnesses. Additionally, the indiscriminate use of antimicrobials may contribute to increased antimicrobial resistance. Consequently, navigating the decision to prescribe antibiotics for LRTIs is a significant concern. Therefore, considering the aforementioned factors, we conducted a prospective observational study to investigate the prevalence, risk factors, and management approaches for lower respiratory tract infections at a tertiary care teaching hospital

2. Methodology

This prospective observational study was conducted at a tertiary care teaching hospital to investigate the prevalence, risk factors, and management of lower respiratory tract infections (LRTIs). The study followed an observational design to assess these aspects over a specified period. The study population consisted of patients presenting with symptoms suggestive of LRTIs, who were admitted to or sought treatment at the tertiary care teaching hospital during the study period.

Data collection involved the systematic collection of information about the prevalence of LRTIs, potential risk factors associated with the development of these infections, and the various management approaches employed for treating LRTIs at the hospital. Standardized data collection forms were utilized to gather information on demographic characteristics, clinical features, diagnostic investigations, treatment regimens, and outcomes of patients diagnosed with LRTIs.

The study protocol was approved by the institutional ethics committee, and informed consent was obtained from all participants or their legal guardians before data collection. Data analysis was performed using appropriate statistical methods to determine the prevalence rates, identify risk factors associated with LRTIs, and evaluate the effectiveness of different management strategies implemented at the tertiary care teaching hospital.

Study design: A Prospective Observational Study.

Study site: Department of General Medicine, Basaweshwar Teaching and General Hospital, Kalaburagi,

Study population: Patients attending the General Medicine Department having lower respiratory tract infections.

Study duration: 6 months

Sample size: 100 cases

Selection criteria: Individuals seeking medical care at Basaweshwar Teaching and General Hospital due to lower respiratory tract infections.

2.1. Inclusion criteria

- Individuals aged 18 years and older.
- Patients of any gender.
- Individuals diagnosed with confirmed lower respiratory tract infections.
- Lower respiratory tract infections caused by bacteria or viruses.

2.2. Exclusion criteria

- Patients with active tuberculosis, COVID-19, or lung cancer.
- Pregnant or breastfeeding individuals.
- Patients who decline to participate in the study.

3. Results

A total of 100 cases of LRTI were collected from the General Medicine Department which includes both male and female populations in an age range of 18-90 years. Out of a total number of 100 cases, 60% were male and 40% of the patients were female. More cases are recorded in patients below 60 years of age. The distribution of gender and age are shown in Figure 1 and 2. The maximum number of cases were seen in the age group range 50 - 59. A total of 19 cases were reported to be recurrent out of 100 cases. These cases had previously been diagnosed with respiratory infections and symptoms such as COPD, Bronchiolitis, Tuberculosis, Pulmonary Koch's, Covid, Bronchial Asthma, and emphysema along with other illness history such as Diabetes mellitus, hypertension, and chronic kidney disease

Figure 1 Distribution of patients based on gender

Figure 2 Age group distribution

Various risk factors were assessed from all the observed cases. The most common risk factor was a weakened immune (76 cases), followed by an age factor. 72 cases out of 100 were below 60 years old. The other two major risk factors were addictions (60 cases) and gender with a predominance of LRTI in male gender (60 cases). The results are shown in Table 1.

Table 1 Risk factors for LRTI

Risk Factors	Findings	Results (No of cases found)
Age	Age < 60 years	72
	Age > 60 years	28
Gender	Predominance in Males	60
Immune status	Weakened Immune system/ Immunocompromised	76
Addictions	Smoking / Alcohol abuse	60
Metabolic Disorder	Diabetes Mellitus Hypertension	25

Figure 3 Graph showing the count and % of patients with addiction

The most commonly prescribed drugs are Antibiotics like Ceftriaxone, Levofloxacin, Amoxicillin + Clavulanate, Azithromycin, Doxycycline, Piperacillin + Tazobactam, Clindamycin and Bronchodilators which include Deriphyllin, and inhalational drugs such as Salbutamol, Budesonide, Ipratropium and Albuterol were given through Nebulizer. Supplemental oxygen was given as a support. The results are shown in Figure 4.

Figure 4 Drugs prescribed for different types of LRTI

In diagnosing respiratory infections, clinical, radiological, and laboratory methods are used. Out of 100 cases, 56 underwent sputum culture tests, with 32 cases of LRTI identified. Streptococcus pneumoniae was the most prevalent microbe (31%), followed by gram stain-positive diplococci (17%). Chest X-rays and CT scans were utilized in cases without culture test results. The results are shown in Figure 5.

Figure 5 Graph showing the causative agents of LRTIs

4. Discussion

In the present study, we have performed a prospective observational study on the prevalence, risk factors, and management of Lower Respiratory Tract infections at a tertiary care teaching hospital. In the present study evidence of LRTI was observed in 100 patients. Out of 100 patients, 60 no. of cases were males which is 60% and 40 no. of cases were females which is 40%. Hence, there is a predominance of the male population in the study. This is by a study conducted by Gurjeet Singh et.al (2013) [8] in Navi

Mumbai. A few other studies conducted by Sunil Vijay and Gaurav Dalela (2016)⁹ in Rajasthan and Syed Mushtaq Ahmed (2013)⁹ in North Kerala have also reported similar results.

The analysis of age-wise data portrait and increased prevalence in the 50-59 age group (22%) was on par with the findings of studies conducted by Sunil Vijay and Gaurav Daalela (2016)⁹. In contrast with similar studies conducted by Gurjeet Singh et.al (2013) and Syed Mushtaq Ahmed (2013)¹⁰ have reported predominance in patients aged 60 and above [10,11].

The most predominant infection (LRTI) in our study was found to be Pneumonia (40%) followed by Pneumonia with Chronic Obstructive Pulmonary Disease (22%), Community-Acquired Pneumonia (22%), Bronchitis (15%), and Hospital Acquired Pneumonia (1%).

The diagnosis was made based on clinical, radiological, and laboratory findings. Imaging studies like X-ray and Computerised Tomography (CT) scans were done in most of the cases. Sputum smear examination (culture test) for identification of microorganisms was done in 56 cases, out of which 32 cases of LRTI were found to be caused by Streptococcus pneumoniae which were the most predominant (31%), followed by gram stain-positive diplococci(17%), pneumococcus (2%), gram-negative bacilli pseudomonas aeruginosa(2%) and Klebsiella pneumoniae(1%), one case each of Staphylococcus aureus (1%) and atypical microbe Mycoplasma pneumoniae(1%), with one mixed infection(1%) in bilateral pneumonia. In the remaining cases, there were no reports of sputum culture tests. [12]

Some of the other studies conducted by M.Ieven et.al (2018) in European countries, Syed Mushtaq Ahmed et.al (2013)¹⁰ in North Kerala, Shaker Salehi, Salman Khan et.al (2015) in Nepal, Thairu et.al (2019)¹² and Ritty Sara (2020) in Bengaluru have also reported Pneumonia as the commonest LRTI with Streptococcus pneumoniae as the predominant microbe. In contrast to our findings, studies conducted by K.V Ramana et.al (2013)¹³ and Sunil Vijay (2016)¹⁴ have reported Klebsiella pneumoniae as the major causative microorganism for LRTI. The most predominant symptoms reported were fever, cough, runny nose, dyspnea, increased purulent sputum, and fluid retention in the lungs. Specific treatments prescribed for various LRTI observed in the study were Antibiotics like Ceftriaxone, Clindamycin, Piperacillin + Tazobactam, Levofloxacin and Amoxicillin + Clavunate. Bronchodilators which include Deriphyllin, and inhalational drugs such as Salbutamol, Budesonide, Ipratropium, and Albuterol were given through Nebulizer. Supplemental oxygen was given as a support [13]

Major risk factors were found to be a weakened immune system (76 cases), followed by smoking and alcohol abuse (60 cases), male gender (60 cases), age below 60 years (72 cases), and metabolic disorders like diabetes mellitus (25 cases). Hence, immune status, addictions, gender, and age were found to be the frequent risk factors in the study.

A total of 19 cases were reported to be recurrent out of 100 cases. These cases had previously been diagnosed with respiratory infections and symptoms such as COPD, Bronchiolitis, Tuberculosis, Pulmonary Koch's, Covid-19, Bronchial Asthma, and emphysema along with another illness history such as Diabetes mellitus, hypertension, and chronic kidney disease. [14]

Sputum examination was carried out in most of the cases and received specific treatment, while other final diagnoses were based on clinical and radiological X-ray and Computerised Tomography (CT) scan findings and were given empirical treatment. Hence, there is a need to confirm aetiological diagnosis to improve the management of LRTI through culture tests so that the specific treatment can be and recurrence is avoided.

5. Conclusion

In our study spanning six months, we documented 100 cases of Lower Respiratory Tract Infections (LRTI), with a notable prevalence among males and a higher incidence observed in individuals under the age of 60. Pneumonia emerged as the most common form of LRTI, with 42 cases identified. Treatment was initiated based on clinical evaluations and radiological findings, with common medications including Amoxicillin + Clavulanate, Ceftriaxone, and Levofloxacin, supplemented by nebulizer therapy employing Salbutamol, Albuterol, Budesonide, and Ipratropium, along with supplemental oxygen. The study highlighted weak immune systems and habits like smoking and alcohol consumption as major risk factors for LRTI. Among our cases, 19 instances of recurrence were identified. The primary clinical symptoms reported were cough, shortness of breath, fever, and pulmonary fluid retention. While some cases underwent sputum examination, identifying Streptococcus pneumoniae and various bacillus strains, limited reports were available regarding causative microorganisms and culture sensitivity.

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Author's short biography

Dr. Syed Afal Uddin Biyabani:

Dr. Syed Afal Uddin Biyabani is a highly esteemed figure in the field of Pharmacy Practice, celebrated for his pioneering research and exceptional academic leadership. Dr. Biyabani's fervent dedication to advancing pharmaceutical sciences is evident through his attainment of advanced degrees in the discipline. He is recognized as a prolific author, making substantial contributions to scholarly literature. His research portfolio encompasses a broad spectrum of topics within pharmacy practice, encompassing clinical pharmacy, pharmacoeconomics, and beyond. Renowned for its innovative approach and practical significance, his work has garnered widespread recognition and appreciation. Additionally, Dr. Biyabani serves as an inspiring educator and mentor, imparting his wealth of knowledge and expertise to future generations of pharmacy professionals